

THE EFFECT OF PARENTAL SUPPORT AND THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ON STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES IN SOCIAL STUDIES FOR GRADE VIII AT THE UPTD OF SMP NEGERI 2 PEMATANGSIANTAR

Ester Novela Siregar et al

learning facilities and limited parental involvement in monitoring academic progress can also contribute to unsatisfactory learning outcomes. Therefore, parental involvement is crucial in fostering positive learning habits and improving students’ academic achievements. In addition to parental support, the school environment also plays a significant role in influencing learning outcomes. The school environment consists of physical and social aspects that support the teaching and learning process. Physical aspects include classrooms, school buildings, learning facilities, libraries, and other infrastructure. Social aspects involve interactions between teachers and students, relationships among peers, and the overall school climate. A conducive school environment can enhance students’ concentration, motivation, and participation in classroom activities. However, if the school environment is less supportive, it may hinder students’ academic performance.

Based on preliminary observations conducted at UPTD SMP Negeri 2 Pematangsiantar, several conditions indicate that improvements are still needed in terms of school cleanliness, classroom comfort, and overall learning atmosphere. Some classrooms are less conducive to learning due to noise and inadequate facilities. These conditions may reduce students’ focus and enthusiasm during the learning process. Consequently, such environmental factors can impact students’ learning outcomes, particularly in Social Studies (IPS). Furthermore, data on students’ Social Studies learning outcomes in Grade VIII show that a considerable number of students have not achieved the minimum mastery criteria. In classes VIII-10 and VIII-11, more than half of the students have not reached the expected level of competency. This situation indicates that students’ learning outcomes still require improvement. Considering the importance of parental support and the school environment in influencing academic achievement, this study aims to analyze the effect of parental support and the school environment on students’ learning outcomes in Social Studies for Grade VIII at UPTD SMP Negeri 2 Pematangsiantar. Through this research, it is expected that the findings will contribute to improving collaboration between parents and schools in creating a supportive learning environment both at home and at school.

METHOD

This study used a quantitative approach with a survey method. The purpose of the research was to determine the effect of parental support and the school environment on students’ learning outcomes in Social Studies. The research was conducted at UPTD SMP Negeri 2 Pematangsiantar. The population consisted of 349 Grade VIII students, and the sample was 66 students from classes VIII-10 and VIII-11 selected using purposive sampling. Data were collected through questionnaires that had been tested for validity and reliability. The data were analyzed using multiple linear regression with the help of SPSS to examine both partial and simultaneous effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Uji Regresi

Tabel 1
Hasil Uji Analisis Regresi Linier Berganda

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	50,588	4,448		11,373	,000
	Dukunganorangtua	,192	,061	,328	3,178	,002
	Lingkungansekolah	,246	,050	,506	4,900	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Hasilbelajar

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression test in the table above, the following regression equation was obtained:

$$Y = 50.588 + 0.192X_1 + 0.246X_2$$

Information:

- X_1 = Parental Support
- X_2 = School Environment
- Y = Learning Outcomes

The equation shows that every increase in the variables of Parental Support (X_1) and School Environment (X_2) will be followed by an increase in the variable of Learning Outcomes (Y). A positive regression coefficient

THE EFFECT OF PARENTAL SUPPORT AND THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ON STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES IN SOCIAL STUDIES FOR GRADE VIII AT THE UPTD OF SMP NEGERI 2 PEMATANGSIANTAR

Ester Novela Siregar et al

value indicates that the relationship between the two independent variables and student learning outcomes is unidirectional (positive), meaning that the higher the parental support and the better the school environment, the more student learning outcomes will also increase. The test results show that the Sig. value of Parental Support = 0.002 and Sig. School Environment = 0.000, both of which are smaller than the 0.05 significance level. This means that both variables have a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes. Thus, it can be concluded that Parental Support and School Environment together have a positive and significant effect on learning outcomes. Therefore, the regression model is declared feasible and valid for use in research.

t-test (Partial)

Table 2
t-Test Results (Partial)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	50,588	4,448		11,373	,000
	Parental support	,192	,061	,328	3,178	,002
	School environment	,246	,050	,506	4,900	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

Based on the results of the t-test (partial) in the table above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The Parental Support variable (X1) has a t-value of 3.178 with a significance value of 0.002, which is also smaller than 0.05. Thus, Parental Support has a positive and significant effect on Student Learning Outcomes (Y). This means that the higher the parental support given to students, the higher the student's learning outcomes will be.
2. The School Environment variable (X2) has a t-test value of 4.900 with a significance value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the School Environment has a positive and significant effect on Student Learning Outcomes (Y). This means that the better the school environment, the more student learning outcomes will improve.

Thus, it can be concluded that the two independent variables, namely Parental Support (X1) and School Environment (X2) have a positive and significant partial effect on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Studies subjects in class VIII.

F test

Table 3
F Test (Simultaneous)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64,405	2	32,203	15,773	,000 ^b
	Residual	128,625	63	2,042		
	Total	193,030	65			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes
b. Predictors: (Constant), Parental support, School environment

Based on the results of the F test (simultaneous) shown in Table 4.9, it is known that the F count value is 15.773 with F table of 3.14 at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, and the Sig. value is obtained = $0.000 < 0.05$. Because F count (15.773) > F table (3.14) and the significance value is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus, simultaneously, the variables of Parental Support (X_1) and School Environment (X_2) have a positive and significant influence on Student Learning Outcomes (Y) in Social Studies. This means that increased parental support accompanied by a conducive school environment will have a positive impact on improving student learning outcomes. In other words, the higher the role of parental support and the better the school environment, the better student learning outcomes will be.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 4
 Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	,578 ^a	,334	,312	1,429
a. Predictors: (Constant), Parental support, School environment				
b. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes				

The R Square value of 0.334 indicates that 33.4% of the variation in student learning outcomes can be explained by the variables of School Environment and Parental Support, while the remaining 66.6% is influenced by other factors outside this study, such as learning motivation, learning interest, teacher learning strategies, and available learning facilities and infrastructure. Thus, it can be concluded that School Environment and Parental Support have a significant influence on Student Learning Outcomes. Although the influence is not too large, both factors play an important role in improving student learning outcomes, especially in Social Sciences subjects. This means that there is a significant relationship between Parental Support and School Environment with Student Learning Outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The discussion of the results of this study aims to explain the answers to the established problem formulation, namely regarding the presence or absence of the influence of the Role of Parents and the School Environment on the Learning Outcomes of Grade VIII Students in Social Sciences (IPS) in the 2024/2025 Academic Year. This research is a quantitative study, because it uses numerical data that is processed statistically to draw conclusions that apply generally to the population. The main objective of this study is to test the previously formulated hypothesis through a series of statistical tests including the normality test, multiple linear regression test, t-test (partial), F-test (simultaneous), and coefficient of determination (R^2) test. Based on the results of data analysis using the multiple linear regression method, the following regression equation is obtained:

$$Y = 50.588 + 0.192X_1 + 0.246X_2$$

The equation shows that if the parental role (X_1) and school environment (X_2) variables are zero or constant, then the value of student learning outcomes (Y) remains at 50.588. In other words, the constant value describes student learning outcomes without being influenced by the two independent variables. Meanwhile, the regression coefficient of the parental role variable is 0.192 and the school environment is 0.246 indicating a positive relationship. This means that every one unit increase in the parental role or school environment will be followed by an increase in student learning outcomes by the value of the coefficient, assuming the other variables are constant. The results of the partial test (t test) show that the parental role variable has a calculated t value of 3.178 with a significance value of 0.002, while the t table value is 1.976 at a significance level of 5%. Because the calculated t value is $>$ t table and significance is $<$ 0.05, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the role of parents has a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes. These findings confirm that parental support in the educational process, whether in the form of attention, motivation, or provision of learning facilities, has a significant contribution to improving student learning outcomes.

The higher the level of parental support and involvement, the greater the encouragement for students to study diligently and achieve optimal performance. Furthermore, the results of the partial test on the school environment variable showed a calculated t value of 4.900 with a significance value of 0.000, while the t table was 1.976. Because the calculated t value $>$ t table and significance $<$ 0.05, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This indicates that the school environment also has a positive and significant influence on student learning outcomes. Good school environmental conditions — such as a comfortable learning atmosphere, adequate facilities, and harmonious social relationships between teachers and students — can increase student learning motivation and have a direct impact on improving learning outcomes. Thus, it can be concluded that the more conducive the school environment, the higher the student learning outcomes. Based on the results of the simultaneous test (F test), the calculated F value was 15.773, which was greater than the F table of 3.06, with a significance value of $0.000 <$ 0.05. These results indicate that the variables of the role of parents and the school environment together have a positive and significant influence on student learning outcomes. Thus, the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This means that the combination of parental support and a good

school environment provides a real contribution in improving student learning achievement in social studies. Furthermore, the results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) test show an R Square value of $0.334 \times 100\% = 33.4\%$, which means that 33.4% of the variation in student learning outcomes can be explained by the role of parents and the school environment simultaneously. While the remaining 66.6% is influenced by other factors outside this research model, such as learning motivation, learning interest, learning style, and learning methods applied by teachers. This relatively small R^2 value indicates that although the role of parents and the school environment have a significant influence, there are still many other factors that determine student learning outcomes. Overall, the results of this study strengthen the view that student learning success is not only determined by individual abilities, but also by external environmental support. The active role of parents and a conducive school environment complement each other in forming positive learning habits, fostering a sense of responsibility, and improving student academic achievement. Therefore, schools and parents are expected to continue to synergize in creating a supportive learning atmosphere so that student learning outcomes are increasingly optimal.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussions outlined in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. **The Role of Parents Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Student Learning Outcomes.**
The results of the partial test (t-test) show that the parental role variable has a calculated t-value of 3.178, greater than the t-table of 1.976 with a significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$. This means that the role of parents has a positive and significant influence on the learning outcomes of eighth-grade students in social studies. Thus, the higher the level of support, attention, and involvement of parents in student learning activities, the higher the learning outcomes achieved by students.
2. **School Environment Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Student Learning Outcomes.**
Based on the t-test results, the calculated t-value was 4.900, which is greater than the t-table value of 1.976, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This indicates that the school environment also has a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes. A conducive, safe, comfortable school environment with adequate learning facilities can increase students' enthusiasm and motivation to learn, thus impacting better learning outcomes.
3. **The Role of Parents and the School Environment Together Influence Student Learning Outcomes.**
The results of the simultaneous test (F test) show that the calculated F value is 15.773, greater than the F table of 3.06 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that both independent variables, namely the role of parents and the school environment, simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes. In other words, the better the parental support and the more conducive the school environment, the more significant the student learning outcomes will be. Based on the results of the determination coefficient test, the R Square value is 0.053, which means that 5.3% of the variation in student learning outcomes can be explained by the role of parents and the school environment together. Meanwhile, the remaining 94.7% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study, such as learning motivation, learning interest, learning methods, and students' intellectual abilities.

REFERENCES

- Berger, P. L., & Luckmann, T. (1966). *The social construction of reality: A treatise in the sociology of knowledge*. New York: Anchor Books.
- Gudykunst, W.B., & Kim, Y.Y. (2003). *Communicating with strangers: An approach to intercultural communication* (4th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Hall, E. T. (1976). *Beyond culture*. New York: Anchor Books.
- Hovland, C. I., Janis, I. L., & Kelley, H. H. (1953). *Communication and persuasion: Psychological studies of opinion change*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Ministry of Environment and Forestry. (2021). *Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia Number 9 of 2021 concerning Social Forestry Management*. Jakarta: KLHK.
- Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas. (2020). *National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) 2020–2024*. Jakarta: Bappenas.

THE EFFECT OF PARENTAL SUPPORT AND THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ON STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES IN SOCIAL STUDIES FOR GRADE VIII AT THE UPTD OF SMP NEGERI 2 PEMATANGSIANTAR

Ester Novela Siregar et al

- Ministry of Environment and Forestry. (2022). Indonesia's FOLU Net Sink 2030: Operational plan. Jakarta: KLHK.
- Littlejohn, S. W., & Foss, K. A. (2011). Theories of human communication (10th ed.). Long Grove, IL: Waveland Press.
- Mulyana, D. (2010). Communication Science: An Introduction. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Rogers, E.M. (2003). Diffusion of innovations (5th ed.). New York: Free Press.
- Soekanto, S. (2012). Sociology: An introduction. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Ariyani, Angelika Putri. Evaluation of the Persuasive Communication Skills of Anti-Bullying Legal Information Counselors. Diponegoro University, 2017.
- Bachtiar, Ebit Eko, Andi Alimuddin Unde, and Tuti Bahfiarti. 2025. Persuasive Communication Strategy of Agricultural Extension Workers in Utilizing Internet Media for Information Dissemination in Women Farmers Groups (KWT) in Ponorogo Regency. Triton Journal 16 (1): 15–26.
- Cindra, Diah Aulia. Persuasive Communication Strategy of Religious Instructors in Motivating Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) to Obtain Halal-Certified Products in Pesanggrahan District, South Jakarta. Thesis, Faculty of Da'wah and Communication Sciences, UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta, 2024.
- Central Kalimantan Provincial Forestry Service. 2021. Central Kalimantan Provincial Forestry Service Strategic Plan 2021–2026. Palangka Raya: Central Kalimantan Provincial Forestry Service.
- Eviany, Eva, and Alexander. 2020. "Vegetation Type Composition on Peatlands in Sebangau National Park, Central Kalimantan." *Sylva Lestari Journal* 8 (3): 352–362.
- Kalima, Titi, and Denny. 2019. "Species Composition and Structure of Peat Swamp Forest in Sebangau National Park, Central Kalimantan." *Journal of Forest Research and Nature Conservation* 16, no. 1: 51–72. <https://doi.org/10.20886/jphka.2019.16.1.51-72>
- Ministry of Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia. 2025. Press Release Number: SP. 031/HKLN/PPIP/HMS.3/03/2025: Forests and Deforestation in Indonesia in 2024
- Ministry of Forestry. 2025. Ministry of Forestry Statistics 2024, Vol. I 2025. Jakarta. P. 169
- Civil Society. 2024. Brief Paper: 20 Million Hectares of Forest by 2025. Indonesia: Civil Society Coalition for Forest Rescue.
- Nugraha, Dwiyan, Latipah, Rosmawati, Siti Normulyana, Syifa Alisya, and Fatmawati. 2024. "Causes of Forest Fires in Central Kalimantan in 2019 and Their Impact on Various Aspects of Life, Indonesia." *Jurnal Cahaya Nusantara* 1, no. 1: 1–6.